

Coordination Chemistry of Quinquevalent Molybdenum-II. Oxypentachloromolybdic (V) Acid

H. K. Saha and M. C. Haldar

Molybdenum in its quinquevalent state forms compounds¹⁻³ of the type $M'_5[Mo_5OCl_5]$ (where $M' = NH_4^+$, Rb^+ etc. and various organic bases) but, actually, nothing is known about the acid $H_5[Mo_5OCl_5]$. However, this acid has been isolated for the first time by us.

The acid has been isolated as bright green crystals by the reduction of molybdic acid with hydrogen iodide in concentrated hydrochloric acid medium. The substance is very unstable towards air and moisture, with water it gives brown solution which is acidic to litmus. Analysis has been carried out by usual procedure⁴. Analytical data closely corresponds to $H_5[Mo_5OCl_5]$, $2H_2O$. *Found*: Mo, 29.65%, Cl, 54.89%; *Calculated* for $H_5[Mo_5OCl_5]$, $2H_2O$, Mo, 29.32%; and Cl, 54.13% (Mo: Cl=1: 5.00). Oxidation state was determined by ceric sulphate method and it corresponds to 5.

Magnetic susceptibility was measured in Guoy balance and was found to be $\mu_{eff.} = 1.62$ B.M. which is in excellent agreement with one unpaired spin of quinquevalent molybdenum.

U. V. measurements were carried out in Beckman DK-2 automatic ratio recording spectrophotometer and 7.3×10^{-4} M solution in water shows a sharp absorption maximum λ_{max} at 315 μ .

Thermogravimetric analysis curve shows that the composition begins to change at about 300° and attains constancy at about 400°. The residue left at 700° quantitatively agrees with its expected conversion to molybdenum trioxide. Weight of the acid taken: 63.50 mg. and residue left: 27.20 mg.; *Calculated* MoO_3 —27.89 mg., (the apparent decrease may be due to slight volatility of MoO_3 at this temperature). The acid on keeping in vacuum desiccator over solid KOH gradually undergoes loss in weight and in a period of few days attains constancy. The substance at this stage loses its green color and turns bluish which is hardly soluble in water.

Conductivity measurements were made in a dipping type conductometric cell. The results indicate that the substance undergoes extensive hydrolysis and polymerisation in water and agrees with the observations of previous workers²⁻⁴ on the salts of this acid.

1. M. C. Haldar and H. K. Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 231.
2. R. G. James and W. Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2145.
3. F. G. Angell, R. G. James and W. Wardlaw, *ibid.*, 1929, 2578.
4. E. A. Allen, et al; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, Part 4, 4649.

Further work in this line with oxypentachloro molybdic (V) acid and its different salts in solid state and solution including their reactions with different inorganic and organic ligands is in progress which will be published later on.

Our grateful thanks are due to Professor P. B. Sarker and Dr. N. N. Ray for giving laboratory facilities and encouragement.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
92 ACHARYA PRAFULLA CHANDRA ROAD,
CALCUTTA-9.

Received, May 8, 1967